

Asynchronous discussion: Inside the LMS or on the open web?

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Abstract: We teach natural science subjects for nursing students. When our students have asynchronous discussions in forums inside the LMS, we see a distribution where around 33% of the students participate a lot, 33% to some extent and 33% participate in little extent. Some scholars suggest that students' discussions should be on the open web so that the students can make connections outside the class. However, one of the critical factors to get the discussions going is a safe environment. The subjects we teach cover an area where real patients' stories are important. Due to ethical concerns, patients' stories should never be published on the open web. How to handle these dilemmas? Do we have examples where discussion on the open web has worked well and engaged almost all students in an unselected student group? And more specifically: Do we have good examples of open discussion in training for the health care sector?

The dilemma

Blended learning (Garrison and Kanuka 2004) is growing in popularity in the Scandinavian countries these years. We teach medicine, anatomy, physiology and pharmacology in nurse education in Norway; teaching full-

time and part-time students. When our students discuss the subject area in forums inside the LMS; we have started to recognize a 33-33-33-distribution, where around 33% of the students participate a lot, 33% to some extent and only 33% participate to a little extent. Almost no students stay silent in the forums. We are currently investigating this distribution further.

A number of e-learning scholars with a strong presence on the internet suggest that students should take part in discussion outside their class, to get into a bigger learning community. Some examples could be Stephen Downes, who writes in his essay about the future of online learning (Downes 2008) that the educational institutions should facilitate the student's participation in learning communities. Alec Couros is one of the the scholars who have inspired us most to think about the PLN and the advantages of being open. (Couros 2008) Schmidt et al present educational identities that are distributed across the web, and make the case for peer-based assessments based on digital trails. (Schmidt 2009) We are impressed by examples where courses take place on the open web, for instance the courses at the P2PU or massive online open courses like Siemens' and Downes' CCK08.

On the other hand, we see that one of the critical factors that get our students to discuss is a safe environment. In internal evaluations, we find that a main reason for not participating is the fear of writing something 'wrong.' In addition, the subject we teach cover an area where real patients' stories, with facts about patients' the students themselves have met are one of the most important teaching materials. Due to ethical concerns, patients stories or fragments of them should never be published on the open web without explicit patient consent.

The discussion

We would like to use an hour at a roundtable to discuss strategies on how to handle these dilemmas, together with colleagues who work with related problems with their students. Special cases like MOOC or P2PU have open courses where many participate and discuss on the open web under full names or recognizable pseudonyms, but one could argue that the students in these courses are not typical. Do we have examples where open asynchronous discussion on the open web, outside the LMS has worked well and engaged almost all students in an unselected student group? And more specifically: Do we have good examples of open discussion in training for the health care sector?

Our local context

We teach at a nursing school geographically located in Oslo, but with students from the whole country of Norway. Compared with other parts of Europe, Norway is a long, sparsely populated country where a significant part of the population live in remote areas far away from the closest university college.

About half of our students study in part-time classes. These students live in various cities and small communities all around Norway, and travel to study in Oslo 4-8 weeks each year (Bingen 2009a) The rest of the time they do e-learning at their home communities, blended with clinical rotations in health institutions in their local area. The part-time group is the classes where we started with e-learning. During this process, we realized that some of the blended learning techniques have advantages compared to traditional teaching, and started to use blended learning in full-time classes as well. We experience content students with this approach (Bingen 2009a), and have started to see indications that the marks at the written exam get better as well (Bingen 2009b)

Our process toward good blended learning can in retrospect be seen as performed in two steps: The first step was to transmit teaching materials as video recordings accessible over the internet (Bingen 2009a) the second step has been to create forums and other communication areas where the students discuss with their teachers as more or less present moderators, guides on the side. (Bingen 2011)

One of the main theoretical inspirations in this process has been Laurillard, who writes that university education must move beyond delivery of content and include ‘engagement with other in the gradual development of their personal understanding.’ Our forums are on the internet, inside the LMS “It’s Learning.” To get the students started in the forums, we have used techniques from Gilly Salmons e-learning theories. (Salmon 2004) (Bingen 2011)

The same things we have experiences the last ten years are described in the literature: Blended Learning can, through a good mix of face-to-face environments and computer-mediated environments improve the learning. Writing is described as an essential communication form: It becomes collaborative as well as individual in an e-learning environment, where there are meeting areas where students and sometimes teachers can discuss the subject area in an asynchronous way (Garrison and Anderson 2003) We see that writing give more room for reflection, and that the asynchronous nature can be a great advantage to students who often have many work and family obligations.

During the piloting phases we have done repeated internal evaluations. One general tendency in the data material is that a surprisingly high proportion of the students participate in the forums, in contrast to a traditional view of the internet as a place where 90% are lurkers and only a few people participate (Nielsen 2006)

A preliminary finding in our pilot data is a 33-33-33-rule, where 33 percent of students participate extensively, 33% to a moderate degree and 33% in little to no extent. We are currently doing research to investigate this further.

Discussion

Inspiring scholars advocate discussion on the open web, but our first impression is that courses who use these models have student masses that are significantly more technologically literate than the average student. We think we need to discuss regularly which principles of open education could and should be extended to the general student mass. When students have no earlier activity on the open internet, discussion about genital anatomy as a student could end up high on the first page when a future employer google their name. A contribution when studying medicine where the student comes up with a very wrong answer could be the first thing one of their future patients google their name. One could argue that we as teacher have an ethical obligation to protect our students from this sort of situations.

Our nurse students come from a country with high penetration of social media, but are a non-selected group. Some of the students are heavy Facebook users, others had never used social media before they started our course. In open-ended questions, the main reason students have for not participating is that they are afraid of reactions from the big groups, and they want a safe environment. Two very common statements from the students are “I don’t like forums where anyone can read” and “I’m afraid of writing something wrong”. A main reason for participation is the feeling of belonging to a group.

A working theory that we currently do research to clarify is that one of the reasons why we have such a high participation rate in the forums is that the environment is protected. We imagine that protected discussion forums are important in undergraduate education to avoid too many lurkers among the students. In addition we start to recognize a significant correlation between participating in the forums and getting good marks.

Another concern is the extensive use of patients' stories. When we teach medicine inspired by constructivist ideas, communities of practice theory and problem based learning, patients' stories is an essential part. The students will often learn most from discussions of dilemmas around patients they have met themselves in their clinical practice. However, such stories should not be published on the web without explicit, written concern. If the date and the student's name is possible to pick up from the web by a curious reader, it can be quite easy for people who know the patient to realize who the story is about.

We are in the middle of this discussion in Scandinavia at the moment. We believe that it would be of great interest to continue the conversation with an international group of colleagues. The difference between the standard views in the clinical communities and the opinions of people in the social media on the internet often feels like two different worlds.

We think these are important issues at the current state of implementation of e-learning, and believe that our case with education of health personnel is of special interest due to the issues of confidentiality. To what extent are the ideas and ideals of open education reasonable and ethical in other subject areas and in non-selected study groups?

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